

HEADACHE AND MIGRAINE: MODERN APPROACHES TO DIAGNOSIS, EXAMINATION AND TREATMENT

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ABSTRACT

Migraine is a chronic neurological disorder characterized by attacks of throbbing, intense headaches, usually localized to one side of the head. The pain lasts from four hours to three days and is typically aggravated by physical activity, bright light, or loud sounds. The aim of this study was to evaluate the features of migraine diagnosis and the effectiveness of modern examination and treatment methods in patients suffering from headaches. A comprehensive assessment of 120 patients with various forms of headache was conducted. The obtained results demonstrated the high diagnostic value of the clinical criteria of the International Classification of Headache Disorders (ICHD-3), as well as the advantages of modern preventive migraine therapies.

Relevance. Migraine is a neurological disorder whose most common and characteristic symptom is episodic (or regular), severe, and excruciating headache attacks on one (rarely both) sides of the head. Migraine is a chronic condition with episodic exacerbations. Migraine is a fairly common disorder, affecting 17.6% of women and 6% of men. Migraine incidence peaks during the most productive years of life between 25 and 55 years of age. Ninety percent of migraine sufferers experience their first attack before age 40.

Headache is one of the most common neurological symptoms, affecting approximately 40% of the world's population. In recent years, significant progress has been made in understanding the pathogenesis of migraine, developing diagnostic criteria, and introducing modern treatments, including drugs that target calcitonin gene-related peptide (CGRP) [1-3].

According to the World Health Organization, migraine affects over 1 billion people, with the condition being more common among working-age women. Migraine is among the leading causes of temporary disability and decreased quality of life [4-6].

Despite the widespread prevalence of the disease, a significant proportion of patients remain underdiagnosed and undertreated. The introduction of the International Classification of Headache Disorders, Third Revision (ICHD-3) has improved the accuracy of diagnosis of migraine and other primary headaches [7].

Modern advances in pharmacotherapy, including monoclonal antibodies to CGRP and gepant drugs, have opened up new perspectives for the treatment of chronic and refractory migraine [8].

Purpose of the study. To evaluate the effectiveness of modern methods of diagnosis, examination and treatment of patients with migraine and other forms of headache.

Material and research methods. The study was conducted in the neurology department of a multidisciplinary clinic in Fergana. The study included 120 patients aged 18 to 65 years who presented with complaints of recurrent headaches. Inclusion criteria: headaches for at least 6 months; ages 18 to 65 years; informed consent to participate.

All patients underwent the following: anamnesis and neurological examination, diagnostics according to ICHD-3 criteria, assessment of pain intensity using a visual analogue scale (VAS), determination of the impact of the disease on quality of life using the HIT-6 scale, magnetic resonance imaging of the brain, Doppler ultrasonography of the vessels of the head and neck, general clinical laboratory tests.

Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS 23.0. Mean values ($M \pm m$), Pearson correlation coefficient (r), and Student's t-test were calculated. Differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Research results. Among the examined patients, migraine was diagnosed in 72 (60.0%), tension-type headache in 36 (30.0%), and secondary headaches in 12 (10.0%). The analysis revealed a significantly higher pain intensity and degree of limitation of daily activities in patients with migraine (Table 1).

Table 1

Clinical and diagnostic parameters of the examined patients ($M \pm m$)

Indicator	Migraine (n=72)	Control (n=48)	p
Age, years	36,4±1,2	35,8±1,4	>0,05
Frequency of attacks per month	8,6±0,5	3,2±0,3	<0,001
YOURS, points	7,8±0,2	4,1±0,2	<0,001
HIT-6, points	62,4±1,3	48,2±1,1	<0,001
Duration of the disease, years	6,8±0,7	4,2±0,5	<0,05

A strong positive correlation was found between the frequency of migraine attacks and abuse of analgesics ($r=0.67$; $p<0.001$), as well as the level of psychoemotional stress ($r=0.62$; $p<0.001$) (Table 2).

Table 1

Correlation analysis of risk factors for the development of chronic migraine

Показатель	r	p
Частота стрессовых ситуаций	0,62	<0,001
Нарушение сна	0,58	<0,001
Индекс массы тела	0,41	<0,01

The main diagnostic method remains clinical assessment according to ICHD-3 criteria. Migraines are characterized by: attack duration from 4 to 72 hours; unilateral localization of pain; pulsating character; increased pain during physical activity; nausea and vomiting; photo and phonophobia.

Additional diagnostic methods include: MRI of the brain; CT scan of the brain; electroencephalography; Doppler ultrasound; laboratory tests.

Neuroimaging is especially important in the presence of “red flags” such as sudden onset of pain, neurological deficit, cancer, age over 50 years.

Modern migraine treatment methods: stopping attacks. For the treatment of acute attacks, the following are used: nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs; paracetamol; triptans; antiemetics. If NSAIDs are ineffective, switching to triptans is recommended.

Preventive treatment includes modern recommendations: β -blockers (propranolol, metoprolol); topiramate; valproates; amitriptyline; venlafaxine; botulinum therapy; monoclonal antibodies to CGRP; gepants (atogepant, rimegepant).

After 6 months of therapy, the reduction in attack frequency was 28.4% with traditional prophylaxis and 56.7% with anti-CGRP therapy ($p < 0.001$). These results confirm international studies demonstrating the high prevalence of migraine among working-age individuals. A thorough history and application of ICHD-3 criteria remain the foundation of successful diagnosis. MRI and other neuroimaging techniques enable the timely exclusion of secondary causes of headache.

The introduction of drugs that target the CGRP system has significantly improved the effectiveness of preventive treatment. According to current international guidelines, these drugs demonstrate high efficacy and a favorable safety profile in patients with chronic migraine.

Conclusions:

1. Migraine is the most common form of primary headache and is diagnosed in 60% of patients seeking neurological treatment for headaches;
2. The most significant risk factors for migraine chronification are stress, sleep disturbance, and analgesic abuse;
3. The ICHD-3 criteria are highly diagnostic and allow for timely diagnosis;
4. Neuroimaging plays an important role in excluding secondary causes of headache;
5. Modern anti-CGRP therapy provides a more significant reduction in attack frequency compared to traditional treatment regimens;
6. A comprehensive approach to diagnosis and treatment helps improve patients' quality of life and reduce the risk of disability.

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